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Mechanical Sensing in Embodied Agents

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Abstract.

Sensors enable autonomous systems to obtain information about their internal states and the environment for guiding their actions. It is as essential for these sensors to reject disturbances as to gather the correct information. There are numerous trade-offs and considerations in designing these sensory systems. For instance, natural agents evolved a vast diversity of highly optimized sensory organs to perform their tasks. This work focuses on how these sensory systems estimate mechanical stimuli. We look at some of the strategies and design principles found in nature to understand fundamental trade-offs and design considerations when acquiring and processing mechanical information.

1. Introduction

Embodied intelligence advances the argument that a behavior cannot manifest without considering the body, brain, sensors, and environment [1, 2, 3]. This argument expanded the field of inquiry into the sensori-motor system and its interaction with the environment, attributing the role of the mind to the ultimate goal of guiding actions [1]. In the pursuit of differentiating the computational function of the body from the brain, researchers have recently introduced the idea of *morphological computation* [4]. Due to the seamless interdependent nature of the sensori-motor system, it becomes difficult to study each component per se. Nonetheless, in this work, we look at the role of embodiment in the sensory system, particularly that involved with estimating mechanical cues. Hence, we first need to define what mechanical sensing is.

Definition. *Mechanical sensing is the ability of a system to encode mechanical stimuli, e.g., displacement and force, owing to its mechanical properties (intrinsic or structural), and convert them into an electrical signal.*

The role of the sensory system is to gather information about the world and the body in a form that the agent can use to guide its actions. A sensor is then a device that selects and transforms this information into a usable, i.e., electrical, form. Indeed, a signal that undergoes processing can be considered “usable”. Data selection (or reduction) is necessary to ease the processing burden on the agent, both in terms of available memory and computational time. Keeping irrelevant data out of the controller is as a critical function of sensory systems as providing relevant information [5].

Figure 1: Sensing is a time-intensive process that involves the fusion and processing of different cues perceived at different speeds. The sensori-motor system is characterized by the body and sensing morphology and by a trade-off mainly between response time and energy efficiency. The computational effort is highlighted by the loop area of the High-level Controller, Low-level Controller, and Body, reflecting the processing time.

As Fig. 1 shows, the design architecture of the sensori-motor system is primarily governed by the environment that imposes physical constraints, the task at hand, and energy considerations. For example, visual sensors are not well developed in deep underwater animals and tiny organisms without a nervous system (as visual processing is computationally heavy). The speed of information varies on the type of the physical cue. For instance, the speed at which information travels by mechanical waves is limited to the speed of sound in that medium. In contrast, the speed of information is much faster in electric circuits, and it is only limited by the electron drift velocity.

Transduction of information is necessary for the data to be processed by computing hardware. However, transducing an energy form into another has costs in terms of time, energy, and noise addition. This aspect is highlighted in Fig. 1, where the area of the different processing loops is proportional to the processing time. The red loop refers to a purely open-loop mechanical response, providing the fastest response if optimally designed, since this information transformation loop does not involve signal transduction. On the other hand, the loop will be limited in the kind of computational processing it can perform [6]. Hence, it becomes challenging to consider all these factors in designing artificial agents.

The blue and yellow loops in Fig. 1 refer to the transduction and flow of information with a low- and a high-level controller, respectively. These loops can be seen in analogy with vertebrates' peripheral and central nervous systems to clarify this concept. The former needs the signal from external cues to be transduced into an electrical source. Then, the signal is elaborated to produce a motor response. On the other hand, a high-level controller involves more sophisticated cognitive processes, like perception. In this case, the brain organizes, identifies, and interprets transformed sensory information.

Observing natural phenomena and mechanisms can lead to a better understanding of design rules for developing new robots. We look at the sensori-motor system of several natural and artificial agents to find their common threads and analyze the overall role of morphology in sensing and the fundamental trade-offs imposed by delays in the sensory system.

2. Sensing for Control

The brain integrates inputs across multiple sensory modalities to obtain a rich and coherent understanding of the environment [7, 8]. All sensory modalities have their characteristic ranges, bandwidth, and processing difficulties. These differences largely determine the employment of one modality over the other. For example, in humans, auditory signals have a frequency range from 20-20,000 Hz, tactile sensing can go up to 1000 Hz, while visual data have the lowest frequency range. In terms of range, visual signals can travel over large distances compared to the poor range of mechanical signals. As mentioned before, the speed of information varies depending on the type of physical cue. Note that mechanical information can pass through the sensors and the body itself, unlike other physical cues, as shown by the passive morphological response loop in figure 1. This perspective focuses primarily on the sensing of mechanical stimuli. An applied force is a mechanical cue that very diverse organisms (such as microbes, roundworms, insects, and mammals) detect and respond to [9]. It is caused by the actions or by the passive adaptation of the body to the environment, and it induces deformation in the body and sensors. Hence, the placement of the sensors, the interface between the sensor and the environment, and its co-dependency with the morphological properties of the enclosing body play an essential role in what a living organism can sense [10]. This close association also means that every closed-loop sensorimotor response initiated by mechanical sensors can, in theory, be replaced by an open-loop mechanical system [11]. In other words, the controller that performs the computation can be replaced by a mechanical system (with an energy source) to perform the same computation [6]. A closed-loop sensorimotor system would be less sensitive to uncertainties in real-world scenarios under unmodelled disturbances. In contrast, an open-loop mechanical system would be insensitive to sensor noise [11].

2.1. Active vs. passive mechanical response

Every biological agent has a certain degree of passive and active components in responding to environmental instances. Full-state feedback control would provide the best performance measures in robotic design without considering cost, weight, fabrication, noise, and processing delays. However, once we consider real-world scenarios where we have uncertainties in state estimation, partial observability, and delays incurred due to sensory transduction (time constant of the sensor), we inevitably introduce fundamental limitations to the performance of the system [12]. Hence, there is always a trade-off between passive and active responses in an agent deployed in real-world situations.

For instance, a delay in an open-loop system merely causes a delay in its output, while delays in a closed-loop system cause instabilities. There are multiple ways to reduce instabilities. All of them involve the development of a predictive model for delay compensation [13]. When the predictive models become complex, passive (open-loop) or closed-loop responses at low gain become the only viable option. The fundamental limit of passive systems is their inability to inject energy into the system/environment controllably. Next, we look at how some of these trade-offs are handled in nature, the role of sensor morphology in simplifying the transduction process, and, finally, how the body morphology regulates the information structuring in these sensors.

3. Case Studies

3.1. Handling Sensory Delays in the Control Loop

Embodiment plays a major role in short-cutting the control loop in various tasks. As case studies, we report two examples of totally different organisms (humans and fruit flies) that nature created to minimize latencies.

3.1.1. Human Hand Touch plays an essential role in our perception of the environment, our ability to manipulate objects [14], and human social interaction [15]. Tactile information is perceived by receptors in the skin, especially in the hands [16, 17], which can encode various modalities, such as texture, shape, temperature, force, pressure, and pain. Such sensory information is perceived and processed with different coding strategies through the afferent nervous system [18, 19]. However, the processing of tactile information in the brain is time-intensive. Yet, techniques have been developed to handle this delay by using predictive models as previously discussed [13].

The pick&lift task (see Fig. 2) is a prototypical basic manipulation task deeply studied in neuroscience. It consists of different phases of interaction with an object and environment, as indicated in Fig.3. Here, the tactile afferents' responses generated at contact events are known as neural signatures, and they represent critical sensorimotor control points [20]. These control points are used to generate anticipatory control actions to reduce latency. Embodiment plays a primary role since the mechanical deformations, in turn, modify the sensori-motor loop to achieve the overall anticipatory motion [14]. Indeed, the morphology of the fingertip (shown in Fig. 2) plays a role since its deformation produces a complex distribution of stresses that, in turn, affects the mechanoreceptors and the tactile response.

Figure 2: Scheme of the pick&lift task. The thumb and the index fingers contact with the test object and exert a grip force that must overcome the load force (normal to the object surface) to lift the object itself.

In this context, skin wrinkles play a crucial role in the control loop when the hand operates in a wet environment. Notably, the action of wrinkles is reflected in the modulation of grip and load forces throughout a basic manipulation task. This aspect has been studied by performing experiments in a wet environment, where it is known that wrinkles are enhanced. In this context, Keraklas et al. showed that individuals with wrinkles could perform pick&lift better than ones without them. [21]. According to Changizi et al. [22], wrinkles act like channels that draw water away when the fingertip is pressed upon a surface. Therefore, objects are grasped more readily. Indeed, the force required to grip wet objects decreases by 20%, with a value in line with that needed for dry objects [23]. In general, the morphological changes due to wrinkling induce a variation in the mechanical interaction at the fingertip/object interface, and thus in the sensitivity of the inner receptors [24].

3.1.2. Fruit Flies Flying insects have strict control requirements due to the need for energy efficiency and the disastrous implications of control failures. These organisms must minimize sensory delays [25], which are a source of instability in closed-loop control systems. Flight stabilization can be achieved through both active and passive mechanisms. Even though passive designs are the easiest design-wise, active ones are the most recurrent [26].

Figure 3: The information used in a basic manipulation task is encoded in the temporal pattern of spikes in ensembles of tactile afferents. Static contact responses are encoded by the fast-adapting type I (FAI) afferents, whereas slow-adapting type I (SAI) and fast-adapting type II (FAII) tactile afferents encode dynamic events. At subgoal events, tactile afferents burst distinctly when digits make/break contact with an object, while FAII respond when an object is lifted off/released from/on the surface. Adapted from [14].

Figure 4: Transfer time (standardized to the time taken to transfer dry objects with unwrinkled fingers) is shortest for dry objects, independent of wrinkling, but faster for submerged objects with wrinkled (red bar) fingers than with unwrinkled (black bar) fingers ($p < 0.001$). Items are picked up with the thumb and the index finger of the right hand, passed through a hole to the left hand, and put into a box with a hole in the lid. Adapted from [21].

Flying insects have highly-specialized body rotation sensors to reduce the detrimental effects of delays. These sensors can provide electrical inputs directly to motor neurons [27] similar to the reflex pathways (Figure 5). However, this is only possible because they have specialized sensors to measure the relevant state variables and the control mapping from the estimated state to the motor action is relatively simple. The sensory information comes from mechanoreceptors at the

base of the halteres, a dumbbell-shaped organ that actively beats back and forth antiphasic to the motion of the wings. Since a moving object in a rotating reference frame experiences inertial (Coriolis) forces, the mechanoreceptors can measure the forces generated by the halteres that are linearly proportional to the angular velocity of the body.

Figure 5: Fruit flies can respond to sensory information quickly due to their optimized sensor-neuron-motor pathway. Adapted from [27].

3.2. Extended embodiment for sensing

Both the body and the environment are perceived from an egocentric point of view [28]. In this regard, the concept of body is not fixed, and both the dynamics of its changes with respect to the agent and that of items used by an agent can be learned [29]. Concerning these aspects, we describe two cases in which the sensory system can use passive instruments to sense the surroundings and adapt to their changes.

3.2.1. Spiders Tactile sensors found in spider species are specialized for discerning particular mechanical cues [5]. Almost all spider species have poor visual capabilities, probably due to their relatively limited nervous system [30]. Spiders use two very similar sensors for detecting medium flow and contact detection (Figure 6). The medium flow sensors or Trichobothria are among the most sensitive biological sensors observed [31, 10]. They have low base stiffness and behave like a rigid rod that effortlessly moves with a flowing airfield. The trichobothria can easily modify their mechanical frequency response by varying their length. Tactile hairs, a modified morphology of the trichobothria, are specialized to detect contact. They are characterized by a tapered morphology and a much higher base stiffness. These characteristics lead to overall lower deflection at the base of the hair, even stress distribution along the structure, and a nonlinear stimuli response which the spider utilizes to be more sensitive at low forces [32]. Spider slit sensilla is another structure developed for strain sensing and vibrations detection. The slit geometry coupled with the stiffness gradient that arises from a rigid exoskeleton and the soft viscoelastic pad enables ultrasensitive displacement detection [33]. Additionally, spiders also show one of the most pronounced examples of modifying the environment for information structuring [34].

Web-building spiders are a fascinating example of embodiment within the ambient to extend cognition. These animals show complex behaviors like route planning, tactics learning, and adjustment to altered conditions [35]. A part of the acquisition, processing, storage, and use of information is outsourced from the central nervous system [36]. This outsourcing leads to less demanding representations of the external world [37, 38, 39].

The mutual manipulability criterion has been used to assess whether web threads and configurations can be seen as integral parts of the cognitive systems [40]. This criterion is widely used to test the constitutive relevance, i.e., to what extent an entity is relevant to explain

Figure 6: Spider example of how small mechanical design changes affect the sensing principle of the mechanoreceptor. Adapted from [5, 33].

the behavior of a larger system. In the case of spiders, it was investigated whether sensations arising from external devices (the web) are relevant to the brain. If changes in the web lead to changes in the cognitive system and vice versa, then the entity is said to be part of the cognitive system. Nakata et al. found out that spiders can focus on a web portion by varying the pulling force exerted upon a part of the threads. This behavior was shown to enhance capture success [41]. Moreover, this attention can be induced. Whenever preys were exclusively put in the same area of the web, spiders learned to increase the pulling force exerted on those threads and, accordingly, to respond faster to stimuli in that direction [42]. These findings allowed us to conclude that the web threads and configurations are integral parts of the cognitive systems [43].

3.2.2. Whiskers Whiskers are highly sensitive, long, and stiff tactile hairs growing in bunches. Animals use whiskers, or vibrissae, to detect information like the precise location, size, and texture of an object and changes in fluid flow to follow underwater preys or navigate the environment. In living organisms, an applied force does not directly affect sensory receptors. Instead, they are activated by the induced deformations transmitted by mediating tissues. In the vibrissal system, tactile information is conveyed by a receptorless and not innervated whisker hair to follicle mechanoreceptors, which then provide input to the brain [44]. The mechanoreceptors are located at the base of the whiskers, in the follicle-sinus complex [45]. The follicle-whisker junction is rigid, so the whisker acts as a mechanical transducer between the objects being touched and the mechanoreceptors of the follicle-sinus complex.

Interactions between the whisker, its follicle, and the associated intrinsic muscle do not occur at a single point. Instead, it occurs along a few millimeters of the follicle length, which contains mechanoreceptors of several types and spatial orientations. The density of a whisker decreases going from the proximal towards the distal region. Hartmann et al. [46] reported how isolated whiskers exhibit natural resonances and strong damping depending on their length, playing an important role in detecting object boundaries.

Active touch comprises several components, such as motor, physical, mechanical, and neuronal transformations. There is also evidence that pre-neuronal morphological transformations are one of these components. For example, rats push their whiskers against objects during localization to induce meaningful morphological coding through the bending moment at the whiskers. This technique is used to obtain a three-dimensional spatial representation of the environment. Indeed, object position can be efficiently determined from whisker mechanics alone, suggesting a role for pre-neuronal morphological computation in active vibrissal touch [47].

Whiskers work by altering their shape to adapt to a particular situation. In case of damage, the sensitivity of the damaged whisker will be reduced by shrinking the barrel, while the sensitivity of the neighboring parts appears to increase. Different levels of elasticity can be

Figure 7: Fully passive hand with mechanical finger synergies trained for sphere 3-finger grasping on an Hex Socket ($\varnothing = 40\text{mm}$) and on Tape ($\varnothing = 35\text{mm}$) [55] (a) and sensorized soft hand for passive grasping (b). Different hand-environment interactions generate different finger behaviours, hence different sensing responses. Adaptive grasping behaviours allow for repeatable and predictable physical and sensory response.

produced by reshaping the medulla layer. The characteristics of this flexible body are modulated to outsource this computational function to the body. Kaneko et al. [48] were the first to investigate the correlation between the curvature of a flexible wire and tactile information. Nguyen et al. [49] proposed an artificial whisker that could actively adjust its sensitivity when the body length was either trimmed or broken. The design proposed by these researchers is at the basis of the compensation strategy needed to develop an active robotic whisker whose malfunctioning can be compensated by varying their sensitivity and that of their neighborhood. Two current limitations concern the lack of algorithms to evaluate the breakage condition and more evidence that allocating the compensatory action to the body is more practical than involving the central processing units.

3.3. Information self-structuring through the morphology of the body

The kinematic design of the body and its mechanical properties also play an important role in funneling and filtering tactile information. Such adaptations become more relevant for complex systems that rely on dense mechanical information processing for control, as shown in two examples.

3.3.1. “Mechanical” Synergies: Synergy control is a popular method to solve the dimensionality problem without sacrificing flexibility for controlling high Degrees-of-Freedom (DoF) hands [50]. In human hands, synergies map low dimensional inputs to the control of a much larger amount of digits. This enables rapid action and adaptation in changing environments without overburdening the central nervous system.

The neural basis for hand synergies is well understood [50, 51], where signals from the Central Nervous System activate characteristic patterns of muscles. Kinematic synergies are the tendencies of different digits to move together [52], the origin of which is rooted in the physical design of the hand and the interconnected nature of tendons driving different joints [53]. Kinematic synergies have been applied to great success in the control of robotic hands, allowing highly adaptive grasping with two [54], one, and even zero [55] degrees of actuation (Fig. 7).

Kinematic synergies act in tandem with reflexes and higher-level hand control, providing a rapid-acting response to small uncertainties in the environment by dynamically balancing hand-environment interactions over multiple joints. This bypasses the central processing system for incredibly cheap and fast control [55], and conditions the hand morphology to activate mechanoreceptors predictably. One example is the passive redistribution of prehensile grasping forces in compliant hands [56]. Other open-loop passive hands, such as Hughes' piano-playing hand, show the importance of morphology in conditioning hand-environment interactions [57]. In another example from Sanfilippo et al. [58], a modular, sensorized, synergy-driven, compliant hand shows the importance of sensing feedback for dexterity. It can achieve this with relatively simple control and cheap sensors, in part, due to the hand's morphology.

3.3.2. Pre-neuronal Compression: Further than shaping and modulating the response at the receptor, the sensor morphology and its behaviors within a passive dynamical body can contribute to compressing information. The skin of the human hand contains $\approx 17,000$ mechanoreceptors to provide detailed and localized tactile feedback [59]. Physical interactions stimulate these receptors through the complex, nonlinear, viscoelastic skin [60]. Dynamic touch elicits mechanical waves in the tactile frequency range that spread throughout the whole hand [61]. The sheer quantity of raw tactile information would quickly overwhelm our cognitive system. Therefore, this information needs to be compressed. There is evidence to suggest that some compression occurs in the dynamic mechanical response of the skin [62]. Shao et al. showed that dynamic touch elicits mechanical waves that efficiently encode tactile information [62]. Optimal encoding of thousands of natural whole-hand stimuli results in a compact representation with primitive spatiotemporal patterns. This suggests the interplay of body dynamics and the sensory system provides a critical modulation of dynamic tactile information such that it can be encoded with extreme efficiency. Sensing redundancy is essential for more general-purpose systems, such as the human hand, and highly specialized receptors are not relied upon. Dense areas of mechanoreceptors can gather vast quantities of tactile data and preneuronal compression is essential for efficient perception of this tactile information.

4. Discussions

The notion of morphological computation and its related field of soft robotics emphasize the importance of passive adaptation of the body. Although passive adaptation provides an avenue for "cheap" control, several fundamental limits and trade-offs need to be considered. Primarily, passive systems are characterized by their inability to control their energy output, whereas delays in state estimation constrain active systems. Hence, passive responses are more observed in static control tasks like grasping, whereas active control is required in more dynamic tasks (as they involve sharper energy changes). Simple systems that require active show a highly specialized sensory system. This is seen in the case of flying insects and, to a lesser extent, in the mechanoreceptors of spiders. In this case, the sensori-motor loop is easily streamlined to perform the desired task while reducing sensory lag and avoiding instability in the controller. Complex systems rely on passive and active responses with predictive models to overcome the performance limitations due to delayed state feedback. Passive responses reduce the burden on the sensory system and the controller, while the active component maintains the power requirements. This can be observed in the case of the human hand, where passive skin adaptation is used along with closed-loop tactile feedback for manipulation.

Unlike audiovisual sensing, mechanical cues are encoded by highly distributed and dense sensory structures (or receptors). Hence, there is a higher need to pre-process the information before it reaches the nervous system. In nature, we see multiple strategies to achieve this. Primarily, mechanical structures are optimized to yield a highly sensitive response to the desired mechanical cues, measured by the sensory neurons at the base. The tactile sensors found

in spiders and whiskers of mammals are good examples of this. In natural organisms, the topology of the receptors evolved to avoid an unneeded information overload. Moreover, the co-dependency between the sensor and the enclosing body aims at increasing both the robustness to damage and input specialization. Indeed, the sensor and the body cannot be considered two separate entities.

The combination of body and brain will allow artificial systems to cope with real environments [63]. Indeed, the biomechanical principles of many biological sensory organs can be identified and classified according to the functionality and the environment in which they operate [10]. On the artificial side, there are still some bottlenecks related to the manufacturing complexity of the materials[64] and in tuning three-dimensional fabrication technologies to obtain specific robust morphologies of sensors in the body. In any case, the major challenge resides in the absence of a well-structured framework that allows full co-design and co-evolving of materials, structure, and control to achieve pre-determined functionalities.

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